

TEACHING MEDIA AND THE ROLE OF TEXTBOOKS IN THEM

Nasimov A.A.

Head of the Samarkand Regional Department of Higher Education,
Science and Innovations

Rakhimov M.E.

Director,

Soliev A.T.

Deputy Director for Vocational Education,

Nazarov A.M.

Head of Production Training. Samarkand Transport Texnikum

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the issues of disclosing the essence, meaning, place and function of textbooks in the process of renewable higheducation, the war all structure and methods of presentation. In particular, based on a review and analysis of dictionary, encyclopedic and regulatory sources, the essence, meaning, functions and features of the textbek in higher education are revealed, and proposals for their improvement are given.

The renewal of the content of higher education in our republic requires the development and implementation of new approaches to the creation of textbooks and teaching aids. Their content should fully reflect international experience, the country's modernization and scientific and technological progress. This, in turn, will become an important factor in the training of highly qualified and competitive specialists.

Indeed, the "Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF5847 dated October 8, 2019, lists among the current problems and shortcomings facing the higher education system in terms of training highly qualified personnel: "The shortage of educational literature remains, and most of the existing ones do not meet the requirements of the time, work on improving the quality of educational literature, using foreign literature as additional or alternative educational literature is insufficient.

Organization "not done" emphasized .

In particular, the credit module system current to do under the circumstances students independent education and his/her educational - methodological supply separately relevance profession This is own in turn , modern study literature create and existing ones update , in particular modern textbooks importance further is increasing . The arrow is of literature role and in importance happened happening of changes essence , they (textbook) and study manuals) teacher's education to give functions in themselves more from embodying As a result, the textbook and study manuals provide passive information from caregivers assuring didactic results to the system turning around, enabling this system to provide students with

self-control and one-stop checks to provide results, logical thinking provides qualifications and language culture to form help gives.

Modern study literature important didactic tool students independent education organization to grow and done increase for be grateful conditions. Students and study in literature software materials necessary at the level to learn for realistic to opportunities has to be must . Study literature with one in line education to the process audiovisual tols and multimedia technologies also more current is being done . Similarly , education technician tols wide used , they students knowledge programmed in the form control to do and simple education functions are doing this . devices to the complex united , students audience practice to their training readiness level or in training new materials acceptance to do over control instaton oppon oppon. From this except , they students are independent in preparation also applied and oneselfoneselfcontrol to do function will do .

The Internet development attitude with remote education for big opportunities to the body came. But , new information carriers to the existence regardless , they of the bok instead press can't , traditional boks still far time education in the system applicant and to knowledge source become The role of modern educational literature as an an active didactic tool is increasing, and working with them creates offers opportunities for sonto studes check, and to stimulate indepentent and creative scientific activity. Educational literature study science its content, theoretical basics and methodological the device expressing, students scientific literature with to work interest also encourages and creative abilities develops .

Education to the means systematic approach used , they to the composition incoming of elements content determination , mutual related terms open to give and structure to study opportunity gives . Every one study science according to education of tools complex learnable science content , learning in the plan designated of training organizational forms , students of activity types – lectures and they with together practical training , course works to perform and this etc. with is determined .

The system of educational tools includes:

- educational literature (textbooks, educational and teaching-methodical manuals, methodological instructions, etc.);
- audiovisual guides;
- a depiction or reflection of objects and phenomena (drawings, models, maps, diagrams, tables, etc.);
- educational and laboratory equipment;
- automated and technical means.

Of educational tools should be developed based on the content of each subject program . The content of the textbook is determined precisely by the subject program, and as an important means of education, it is directly or indirectly connected with all othethols, using the educatol them and influences their content and structurere.

A list of issues that should be covered in the educational process . It does not reveal the content of the knowledge that should be studied, does not determine their volume and depth, as well as the content and description of knowledge, skills and qualifications. The curriculum only indicates what the scientific and theoretical level of teaching should be. Therefore, the

content of the curriculum of a subject must be clearly, comprehensively and in detail disclosed in the textbook.

Therefore, "a textbook is an officially approved main educational publication that systematically, deeply and completely covers the topics of a specific academic subject, is aimed at perfect mastery of the content of the relevant subject in a specified volume, is adapted in content and form to the types of education (secondary specialized, vocational education, higher education (bachelor's, master's)), serves to form knowledge, skills and competencies related to the subject in students, and develops creative abilities."

Therefore, the textbook should present information that is methodologically selected and processed in accordance with the curriculum. In many cases, it is thanks to the textbook that the curriculum is clarified, developed and improved. It is this rule that allows the educational process to apply the most advanced innovations developed in pedagogical science and the experience of leading scientific and pedagogical schools.

Allows you to.

The other hand, textbooks, even practical, laboratory and other types of

Although it includes exercises, educational work may not provide an adequate disclosure of the content of these types of work. Therefore, in addition to textbooks, textbooks, sets of exercises and assignments, laboratory works (practicums), design guides and other educational tools published. The content of educational literature should provide opportunities for the use of other educational tools, including technical means, computers and educational laborerequipment.

Thus, the textbook, along with other educational tools, is a system of presenting knowledge whose components are interconnected. The information embodied in the textbook and included in other educational tools within the framework of the curriculum should be of the same type and presented at the same scientific and methodological level, provide for the use of special literature and be practice-oriented.

The preparation and publication of any educational literature is determined, first of all, by its role and place in the system of specialist training tools, the goals and objectives of education, as well as the characteristics of the book as a means of presenting educational information. The textbook, as an important element of the system of educational tools, familiarizes students with the content of the studied academic subject, the state and prospects for the development of this area of science, technology and culture.

Serves to introduce.

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